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Control Strategies and Adaptive L1/L2 Functionalities for Semantic Communications: First results

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Abstract

This deliverable presents the initial results on control strategies and Layer 1 and Layer 2 (L1/L2) functionalities for semantic and goal-oriented communications. It introduces the basic framework and key functionalities for implementing policy-based semantic control in the Open Radio Access Network (O-RAN) architecture. First, the current O-RAN architecture is reviewed to identify the necessary enhancements to components, standardized interfaces, and operations to support semantic network control. Subsequently, the Semantic RAN Intelligent Controllers (S-RICs) are introduced as core elements of the 6G-GOALS architecture, enabling dynamic, semantic-aware policy enforcement in the RAN. The potential benefits of Machine Learning-based network control via S-RICs are demonstrated in a commercial-grade 5G network deployment. Furthermore, the deliverable proposes semantic-aware L1/L2 functionalities and control strategies for three use cases: 1) Semantic content selection in the Internet of Things (IoT); 2) Heterogeneous IoT; and 3) Collaborative edge inference. Methods for designing and optimizing Medium Access Control protocols and device grouping strategies are developed and evaluated. These methods yield significant improvements in key performance indicators, including energy efficiency, task accuracy, throughput, communication overhead, and top-k Query Age of Information. Overall, this deliverable presents important advancements toward the realization of efficient semantic control in O-RAN, supported by novel L1/L2 functionalities and control approaches.

Keywords

O-RAN, RAN intelligent controller, network orchestration, semantic communication, goal-oriented communication, machine learning, interference management, IoT, energy efficiency, Age of Information, wake-up radio, medium access control, heterogeneous networks, pull communication, push communication, edge inference, accuracy, attention mechanism, optimization.

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

3GPP	3rd Generation Partnership Project
AAL	Accelerator Abstraction Layer
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AMC	Adaptive Modulation and Coding
AP	Application Protocol
BER	Bit Error Rate
BLER	Block Error Rate
CCC	Cell Configuration and Control
CP	Control Plane
CSMA	Carrier Sense Multiple Access
CoWu	Content-Based Wake-Up
CU	Central Unit
DNN	Deep Neural Network
E2AP	E2 Application Protocol
E2SM	E2 Service Model
EE	Energy Efficiency
eMBB	Enhanced Mobile Broadband
eNB	Evolved Node B
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
HARQ	Hybrid Automatic Repeat reQuest
IoT	Internet of Things
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
KPM	Key Performance Measurement
k -QAoI	Top-k Query Age-of-Information
L1/L2	Layer 1 and Layer 2
LSTM	Long Short-Term Memory
MAC	Medium Access Control
MCS	Modulation Coding Scheme
MEC	Multi-Access Edge Computing
ML	Machine Learning
NETCONF	Network Configuration Protocol
ng-eNB	Next-Generation Evolved Node B
NI	Network Interface
Non-RT RIC	Non-Real-Time RAN Intelligent Controllers
OAM	Operations and Maintenance
OOK	On-Off Keying
O-CU	O-RAN Central Unit
O-CU-CP	O-RAN Central Unit - Control Plane
O-CU-UP	O-RAN Central Unit - User Plane
O-DU	O-RAN Distributed Unit
O-eNB	O-RAN Evolved Node B
O-RAN	Open Radio Access Network
O-RAN SC	O-RAN Software Community
O-RU	O-RAN Radio Unit
PDCP	Packet Data Convergence Protocol
PPP	Poisson Point Process
PRB	Physical Resource Block
QoS	Quality of Service
RAI	RAN Analytics Information
RAN	Radio Access Network
RC	RAN Control
RIC	RAN Intelligent Controller

RLC	Radio Link Control
RSRP	Reference Signal Received Power
RSSI	Received Signal Strength Indicator
rApp	Radio Application
RT	Real Time
SDL	Shared Data Layer
SMO	Service Management and Orchestration
SUTD	Singapore University of Technology and Design
UE	User Equipment
UP	User Plane
URLLC	Ultra Reliable Low Latency Communications
V2X	Vehicle-to-Everything
VES	Virtual Event Streaming
WSN	Wireless Sensor Network
xApp	Real-Time Application

1 Introduction

1.1 Objectives of this deliverable

The objective of this deliverable is to introduce the basic framework and key functionalities for implementing *policy-based semantic control* in the Open Radio Access Network (O-RAN) architecture, a critical enabler of semantic and goal-oriented communications. To this end, there is a need to define the Semantic RAN Intelligent Controllers (S-RICs) within the *6G-GOALS Architecture* [6GGOALS-D25]. Specially, the S-RICs are designed as programmable and extensible units to facilitate the deployment of diverse semantic applications.

By extending the current Non-Real-Time RIC (Non-RT RIC) and Near-Real-Time RIC (Near-RT RIC) to enable semantic awareness, the S-RICs offer a rich set of open interfaces for connecting with other O-RAN components, leveraging feedback loop-based control mechanisms to reconfigure and enforce wireless network behaviour dynamically. Ultimately, the S-RICs serve as flexible platforms for deploying Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) applications that adapt the network at different time scales, optimizing it to achieve extreme Energy Efficiency (EE), spectral efficiency, reliability, and robustness.

To enable effective policy-based semantic control in the *6G-GOALS Use Cases* [6GGOALS-D21] [6GGOALS-D23], novel Layer 1 and Layer 2 (L1/L2) functionalities and control strategies are also required. The new adaptive L1/L2 functionalities can operate alone or in coordination with the S-RICs to leverage the semantic paradigm for efficient semantic and goal-oriented communications. In particular, applications in heterogeneous Internet of Things (IoT) scenarios demand Medium Access Control (MAC) protocols that support the coexistence of diverse communication modes and can be optimized to maximize goal-oriented objectives. In collaborative edge inference, control mechanisms must reduce the communication overhead while preserving the task accuracy by prioritizing transmissions that convey relevant information. Finally, semantic content selection for IoT scenarios can benefit from information retrieval strategies based on data relevance and supported by L1/L2 functionalities to significantly reduce the devices' energy consumption.

1.2 Advancements in this deliverable

This deliverable presents the initial advancements of Task 5.1, which focuses on developing control strategies and adaptive L1/L2 functionalities for RIC-centric semantic control. In particular, this deliverable exposes the advancements of this task by exploring:

- *S-RICs for policy-based semantic control in O-RAN*: Extension of the O-RAN's Non-RT and Near-RT RICs for semantic-aware network control, creating the semantic control plane; this new plane supports dynamic network adaptations based on user and application context by receiving semantic-aware requirements and sending policy decisions in response.
- *RIC-based RAN interference management*: Demonstration of ML-based intelligent network control in a commercial-grade 5G network, introducing Radio Applications (rApps) for localization, throughput prediction, predictive maintenance, and inter-cell interference management.
- *Energy-efficient IoT semantic content selection*: Introduction of a MAC protocol based on the wake-up radio technology for timely retrieval of fresh and relevant data, and proposal of its optimization to maximize EE by reducing the IoT devices' power consumption.

- *Harmonious coexistence in heterogeneous IoT:* Optimization of the MAC frame design to maximize the probability of successful communication coexistence of IoT devices using the pull and push communication modes, allocating the time slots dedicated to each mode based on the average incoming traffic.
- *Collaborative inference with low communication overhead:* Proposal of a method for device grouping based jointly on the semantic features of their data and the channel link conditions, capable of achieving high task accuracy with reduced communication overhead.

1.3 Structure of this document

This deliverable is organized as follows. Section 2 reviews the O-RAN architecture and introduces the 6G-GOALS project's advancements in defining the novel S-RICs for semantic-aware network orchestration. It concludes with a demonstration of RIC-centric control techniques deployed via AI-based rApps on a commercial-grade 5G network. Section 3 presents L1/L2 functionalities and control strategies for semantic content selection in IoT scenarios, heterogeneous IoT, and collaborative edge inference. The factors addressed by the proposed methods include EE, communication overhead, and optimization of goal-oriented objectives. Finally, Section 4 concludes this deliverable with remarks on future work.

2 Semantic RAN Intelligent Controllers

This section outlines the current O-RAN architecture and introduces the definition of the novel S-RICs for semantic-aware network orchestration. Specifically, Section 2.1 presents an overview of the O-RAN framework, describing its main components, standardized open interfaces, and RIC operation. Section 2.2 introduces the S-RICs developed in the 6G-GOALS architecture based on the integration of semantic communication principles into the RICs interfaces, operations, and functionalities. Section 2.3 concludes with a demonstration of RIC-centric control methods for localization, throughput prediction, predictive maintenance, and cross-cell interference management deployed by rApps in a 5G network.

2.1 Overview of the current O-RAN framework

2.1.1 O-RAN architecture components and principles

The O-RAN represents a transformative approach aimed at overcoming the limitations of traditional cellular network architectures characterized by monolithic, vendor-specific components. O-RAN embraces four foundational principles that collectively address the growing demands for flexible, efficient, and intelligent RANs by leveraging modern technological advancements and fostering a competitive, innovation-friendly ecosystem [PBD+23].

These principles not only guide O-RAN's evolution but also ensure its alignment and integration with the RAN architecture defined by the 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP). By adopting and extending the specifications set by 3GPP, O-RAN introduces enhanced openness, interoperability, and intelligent control capabilities.

- **Disaggregation:** Splitting the traditional base station into distinct functional units, namely, Central Unit (O-CU), Distributed Unit (O-DU), and Radio Unit (O-RU), allowing each unit to be independently deployed and optimized. This approach promotes flexibility, scalability, and cost-effectiveness, as each component can run on standardized hardware or cloud platforms.
- **Openness and Interoperability:** O-RAN utilizes standardized, open interfaces to interconnect components from various vendors, effectively breaking vendor lock-in and fostering a competitive ecosystem that encourages innovation and rapid adoption of advancements.

- **Virtualization:** Network functions in O-RAN architectures are virtualized, enabling flexible deployment, scalability, and easier upgrades and maintenance through cloud-native technologies.
- **Intelligent, ML-driven Control:** The integration of ML and AI through RICs enables intelligent, data-driven decision-making for dynamic optimization and resource management.

Figure 2-1 Logical architecture of O-RAN.

As described in [ORAN1OAD] and shown in Figure 2-1, the O-RAN architecture comprises several key components, each designed to support and realize the foundational principles outlined above. These components are integral to achieving the objectives of openness, interoperability, intelligent control, and efficient network management, while maintaining consistency and interoperability with 3GPP standards:

- **Service Management and Orchestration (SMO) Framework.** Manages and orchestrates the O-RAN functions, including the Non-RT RIC. It provides policy-driven automation, lifecycle management, and network optimization functionalities.
- **Non-RT RIC.** A critical component of the SMO, operating on a time scale greater than one second. It hosts rApps to provide high-level policy decisions, orchestration of ML models, and intent-based network management.
- **Near-RT RIC.** Operates on time scales between 10 ms to 1 second, providing real-time network optimization through xApps (Real-Time Applications) that manage radio resources, network slicing, scheduling, handovers, and interference management.
- **O-CU-CP/O-CU-UP.** Handles Control Plane (CP) and User Plane (UP) functionalities, respectively. The O-CU-CP manages higher-level signalling functions, while O-CU-UP deals with data traffic handling.
- **O-DU.** Implements lower-layer radio protocol functions such as Radio Link Control (RLC), MAC, and part of the physical layer operations.

- **O-RU.** Conducts physical layer functions such as radio frequency processing and beam-forming, typically deployed close to the antenna.
- **O-Cloud.** A cloud computing platform hosting the O-RAN network functions, providing infrastructure services including virtualization management, lifecycle management, and support for hardware acceleration through Accelerator Abstraction Layers (AAL).
- **O-eNB.** An Evolved Node B (eNB) [3GPP36401] or Next-Generation eNB (ng-eNB) [3GPP38300] [3GPP38401], as defined in 3GPP, that can be integrated in the O-RAN architecture.

In particular, as will be detailed in the following subsections, the two RICs play a fundamental role in achieving intelligent automation within the O-RAN ecosystem. Designed to leverage extensive data collection capabilities, they apply AI and ML techniques for dynamic optimization and automated decision-making processes, enhancing the overall efficiency and responsiveness of the RAN infrastructure. The **Non-RT RIC** provides high-level policy management, orchestration of ML models, and intent-based management. Example functionalities include interference management, network slicing decisions, and optimization at broader geographic scales. On the other hand, the **Near-RT RIC** engages in near real-time control loops, directly interfacing with the radio components to optimize performance, manage network slicing at the user level, and dynamically adjust resources based on live telemetry data.

The standardized open interfaces in the O-RAN architecture are crucial for ensuring seamless communication between its components, thus enabling interoperability and modularity across different vendors. The key interfaces introduced in the O-RAN specifications are:

- **A1 Interface**, connects Non-RT RIC and Near-RT RIC, supporting policy management, ML model management, and information enrichment services [ORAN2A1].
- **O1 Interface**, facilitates management and orchestration from the SMO to all O-RAN Network Functions, ensuring efficient operational administration [ORAN1001].
- **E2 Interface**, provides a direct communication path between Near-RT RIC and E2 nodes (O-DU, O-CU), enabling telemetry collection and dynamic control for real-time optimization [ORAN3E2].
- **O2 interface**, connects the SMO to the O-Cloud infrastructure, enabling management of the underlying cloud resources that host O-RAN functions [ORAN6O2].

These interfaces collectively ensure modular integration and effective interoperability across diverse vendor ecosystems, significantly enhancing the agility, performance, and maintainability of RAN deployments.

2.1.2 Non-RT RIC: Architecture and functionalities

As shown in Figure 2-2, and detailed in O-RAN specification [ORAN2ARC], the Non-RT RIC represents a central component within the SMO framework of the O-RAN architecture. Positioned logically within the SMO, the Non-RT RIC is responsible for higher-level, policy-driven decisions, network-wide optimizations, and AI/ML-driven analytics with operational timelines typically greater than one second. It interfaces indirectly with the Near-RT RIC, influencing its real-time operations through high-level policy directives and optimization strategies.

Architecturally, the Non-RT RIC consists of two primary elements:

- **Non-RT RIC Framework.** Provides core functionalities such as managing policies, orchestrating AI/ML workflows, and facilitating service exposure. It manages interactions with various O-RAN components through standardized interfaces.

- **rApps.** Modular software components hosted on the Non-RT RIC that implement specific use-case-driven functionalities like interference management, coverage optimization, or predictive maintenance. rApps utilize the services exposed by the Non-RT RIC framework to perform their tasks effectively.

Figure 2-2 Non-RT RIC reference architecture.

The Non-RT RIC offers a comprehensive set of services aimed at enabling intelligent, automated network management and optimization. These services include, among others:

- **Service and Data Management.** Ensures efficient data registration, discovery, subscription, and delivery processes. Data from RAN elements and other network entities are managed and exposed to rApps for further processing.
- **A1 Policy Management.** Defines, manages, and distributes policy-based control information to the Near-RT RIC, facilitating indirect influence over near-real-time RAN operations.
- **RAN Operations and Maintenance (OAM).** Provides centralized management of fault, configuration, performance, and other operational aspects of the RAN elements, leveraging data collected through the O1 interface.
- **AI/ML Workflow Management.** Coordinates training, deployment, storage, and monitoring of AI/ML models, enabling dynamic network optimization through predictive analytics and intelligent decision-making.

The Non-RT RIC interacts with other components in the O-RAN architecture through two key interfaces:

- **A1 Interface.** It connects Non-RT RIC to Near-RT RIC and is primarily responsible for policy management and the distribution of enrichment information. Policies managed via the A1 interface influence real-time operations executed by Near-RT RIC by specifying behaviours and performance targets. Additionally, the A1 interface provides Near-RT

RIC with enrichment information derived from non-network or external sources, aiding in enhanced real-time decision-making processes [ORAN2A1].

- **R1 Interface.** It provides robust communication pathways between rApps and the Non-RT RIC framework. It supports multiple essential services such as service registration and discovery, data management and exposure, AI/ML workflow management, and policy management. Through the R1 interface, rApps interact dynamically with the Non-RT RIC framework, allowing them to access and utilize necessary data, services, and functionalities effectively to optimize network performance and reliability [ORAN2R1].

The R1 interface allows to expose services that provide access to functionality related to other key SMO interfaces, and in particular:

- **O1 Interface.** It facilitates comprehensive management operations between the Non-RT RIC and network functions. It supports a variety of operational services, including fault management, performance assurance, and configuration management. Utilizing standardized NETCONF/YANG protocols, the O1 interface enables the Non-RT RIC to effectively monitor, manage, and orchestrate RAN resources, thus ensuring the overall health and efficiency of network operations [ORAN10A1].
- **O2 Interface.** It connects the SMO—including the Non-RT RIC—to the O-Cloud infrastructure, enabling management of the underlying cloud resources that host O-RAN functions. The O2 interface supports infrastructure management, deployment automation, and lifecycle orchestration of network functions, ensuring that cloud-native services can be instantiated, scaled, or updated in alignment with dynamic network demands. This integration enhances the flexibility and cloud alignment of the O-RAN system [ORAN6O2].

Moreover, it should be noted that the architecture in Figure 2-2 includes the possibility for the Non-RT RIC Framework to have external interfaces that can be used to interact with non-network and external sources.

By integrating these functionalities and leveraging standardized open interfaces, the Non-RT RIC enables intelligent, policy-driven network management, significantly enhancing the performance, reliability, and efficiency of O-RAN deployments.

2.1.3 Near-RT RIC: Architecture and functionalities

The Near-RT RIC is a pivotal component of the O-RAN architecture [ORAN3ARC], responsible for managing time-sensitive radio resource management functions with control loop latencies in the range of 10 milliseconds to 1 second. Positioned between the Non-RT RIC and the RAN elements (referred to as E2 Nodes), as shown in Figure 2-3 the Near-RT RIC is structured around two primary building blocks:

- **Near-RT RIC Platform.** This provides the runtime environment, message handling, and service infrastructure necessary to support xApps execution. It manages resource allocation, lifecycle management, and communication with E2 Nodes and other O-RAN components.
- **xApps (RAN Applications).** These are modular applications hosted on the Near-RT RIC that perform specific RAN control functions (e.g., mobility management, load balancing, Quality of Service (QoS) enforcement). xApps operate within the defined E2 Service Models [ORAN3ESM] and leverage the APIs exposed by the Near-RT RIC platform [ORAN3API] to access E2 interface capabilities and to interact with other xApps or components.

Figure 2-3 Near-RT RIC architecture overview.

The Near-RT RIC enables a wide array of functionalities that contribute to more dynamic, granular, and policy-driven control of the RAN. The key components of the Near-RT RIC platform include:

- **Interface Terminations.** These functionalities enable termination of the different interfaces supported by the Near-RT RIC (O1, A1, E2, Y1).
- **xApp Repository and Subscription Management.** These components feature services and APIs for the automated life-cycle management of the xApps. It allows xApps to connect to functions exposed over the E2 interface and it also controls the access that individual xApps can have to E2 messages.
- **Conflict Mitigation.** This component addresses possible conflicts emerging among different xApps, as different, independent xApps may apply conflicting configurations while trying to achieve independent optimization goals.
- **Shared Data Layer (SDL) and Database.** These functionalities enable the Near-RT RIC platform to maintain and expose RAN/UE information and other information required to support specific use cases.
- **AI/ML Support.** Similarly to what happens in the Non-RT RIC for rApps, this enables data pipelining, model management, training and inference for xApps, thus providing complete AI/ML workflow to implement AI/ML algorithms in the Near-RT RIC.
- **Messaging Infrastructure.** The internal messaging infrastructure connects xApps, platform services, and interface terminations to each other with low latency message delivery.
- **Security.** This component prevents malicious xApps from leaking sensitive RAN data or from affecting the RAN performance.

- **API enablement.** This functionality provides support for registration, discovery and consumption of Near-RT RIC APIs within the Near-RT RIC scope. Near-RT RIC APIs can be categorized based on the interaction with the Near-RT RIC platform and can be related to E2-related services, A1-related services, Management related services, and Shared Data Layer services [ORAN3API].
- **Management.** OAM management consists of fault, configuration, accounting, performance, file, security and other management plane services.

The Near-RT RIC can combine different RIC services provided by an E2 node to implement an E2SM. These services are [ORAN3E2]:

- **REPORT:** Near-RT RIC uses a RIC subscription to request that E2 Node sends a REPORT message to Near-RT RIC. The way of report is configured during the subscription in the field: "Event Trigger".
- **INSERT:** Near-RT RIC uses a RIC Subscription to request that E2 Node sends an INSERT message to Near-RT RIC. This message suspends the associated procedure in the E2 Node. The condition to suspends the procedure is described in the field "Event Trigger" contained in the subscription.
- **CONTROL:** Near-RT RIC sends a CONTROL message to E2 Node to:
 - initiate a new associated procedure
 - or resume a previously suspended associated procedure in the E2 Node (when is transmitted after an INSERT procedure)
- **POLICY:** Near-RT RIC uses a RIC Subscription to request that E2 Node executes a specific POLICY during functioning of the E2 Node after each occurrence of a defined RIC Subscription procedure Event Trigger.
- **QUERY:** Near-RT RIC sends a QUERY message to the E2 node to retrieve RAN-related and/or UE-related information from the E2 Node.

The O-RAN Alliance has standardized different E2SMs, categorized by their control or monitoring purposes, such as:

- **E2SM-KPM (Key Performance Measurement)** that reports performance metrics from the RAN, using the E2 report service.
- **E2SM-RC (RAN Control)**, contains REPORT/INSERT/CONTROL/POLICY services. The E2SM RC implements control functionalities through E2 control services. E2SM RC includes a broad set of control domains including radio bearer control, radio resource allocation control, connected mode mobility control, radio access control, etc..
- **E2SM-NI (Network Interface)**, contains REPORT/INSERT/CONTROL/POLICY services. It is used to take the messages received by the E2 node on specific network interfaces and forward them to the near-RT RIC domain via E2 report messages over the E2 interface.
- **E2SM-CCC (Cell Configuration and Control)**, that exposes configuration and control related processes on a cell-level basis.

These models enable fine-grained and extensible control and observation capabilities over the RAN.

As visible in Figure 2-3, besides the already introduced interfaces, the Near-RT RIC supports also the Y1 interface [ORAN3Y1]. The Y1 interface enables interaction between the Near-RT RIC platform and authorized consumers, which can be also external entities. It supports services such as:

- **Y1_RAI_Subscription:** Allows Y1 consumers to subscribe/unsubscribe to RAN analytics information (RAI), and to receive notification of the RAI from the Near-RT RIC.
- **Y1_RAI_Query:** Enables on-demand querying of RAN analytics metrics from the Near-RT RIC.

The Y1 interface typically relies on RESTful HTTP/JSON communication.

Through the integration of its modular xApp-based architecture and rich set of interfaces, the Near-RT RIC is a cornerstone of O-RAN's goal to deliver intelligent, open, and interoperable RAN management and control.

2.2 Semantic-aware RIC operations and challenges

Traditional communication models—built on the transmission and reception of bits with high fidelity—are showing limitations in efficiently supporting such use cases. A promising alternative is emerging in the form of semantic communication, which focuses on transmitting the meaning or intended significance of data rather than the raw data itself. This paradigm offers a radical rethinking of communication theory, with the potential to dramatically reduce bandwidth usage, improve latency, and optimize resource allocation by aligning network operations more closely with application-level goals and user intent. The integration of semantic intelligence into O-RAN, particularly via its intelligent control components—Near-RT RIC and Non-RT RIC—offers a powerful path to building future-ready, adaptive, and context-aware mobile networks.

Despite its promise, integrating semantic communication into the O-RAN framework is a complex endeavour, primarily due to architectural, operational, and standardization challenges that span the entire network stack. One of the most critical limitations in the current O-RAN specification is its insufficient support for end-to-end interactions involving User Equipment (UE) and applications. Specifically, there are no well-defined mechanisms or interfaces to allow the collection of contextual insights or semantic requirements from UEs and applications, nor to enforce decisions or policies back onto these entities in a closed-loop manner. This limitation is especially detrimental to use cases that rely on real-time interpretation and adaptation, such as AI-driven mobility services or dynamic video compression based on content importance. Without these capabilities, the network is restricted in its ability to optimize performance holistically across the user, network, and application planes.

Furthermore, semantic communication relies heavily on a shared understanding of the data's context, which in turn demands standardized formats for knowledge representation. This could involve ontologies, knowledge graphs, or pretrained models that encapsulate domain-specific semantics.

Moreover, the effectiveness of semantic communication depends on timely feedback mechanisms and continuous learning. Semantic models must adapt to changes in context, environment, and user behaviour, which entails ongoing feedback collection, training, and distribution of updated models across the network. In the O-RAN architecture, this necessitates a tight integration of semantic feedback loops across both the Near-RT and Non-RT RICs, as well as coordination with the SMO layer. The computational and signalling overhead introduced by these dynamic learning processes adds to the system complexity, particularly in large-scale or multi-operator deployments. For this reason, as detailed in [6G-GOALS D2.5], the 6G-GOALS consortium design and proposes a Semantic-aware RAN architecture depicted in Figure 2-4

At the device and application layer, they propose the introduction of a Semantic Module and a Semantic Extractor. The Semantic Module, residing within the UE, is responsible for interpreting and filtering information prior to transmission, ensuring that only contextually relevant data is sent across the network. Meanwhile, the Semantic Extractor, operating at the edge or within a Multi-Access Edge Computing (MEC) environment, applies advanced AI models to analyse raw

data streams and extract meaningful content representations. These elements collectively reduce data volume and enhance communication efficiency by transmitting the essence of information rather than its entirety.

Figure 2-4 6G-GOALS Architecture.

At the network control layer, they envision an enhancement of the Y1 interface, a recently introduced O-RAN component that connects the Near-RT RIC to external entities. While the current Y1 interface supports one-way sharing of radio analytics, it must evolve into a bidirectional interface capable of transporting semantic Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), configurations, and policy feedback between RICs and external applications. This will enable the Near-RT RIC to both receive semantic-aware requirements and send optimized policy decisions in response, supporting dynamic network adaptations based on user and application context.

Additionally, the Non-RT RIC must be equipped with capabilities to orchestrate the lifecycle of semantic models, including training, validation, deployment, and retirement. It should also support the enforcement of policy constraints that align semantic inference tasks with privacy regulations and resource constraints. By building a control loop between the Non-RT and Near-RT RICs, the system can continuously learn and adapt to emerging conditions without compromising operational efficiency.

To support interoperability, it is crucial to define standardized semantic data models and knowledge representations that can be shared across all network entities. This requires cross-industry collaboration and may involve contributions to standardization bodies such as the O-RAN Alliance, 3GPP, and European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI). These models should be expressive enough to capture complex context relationships but also lightweight enough to be processed in real-time environments.

2.2.1 Enabling semantic communication in L1/L2 operations

While much of the discourse surrounding semantic communication and intelligent RAN focuses on higher-layer functions—such as AI-driven decision-making, semantic inference, and application-aware resource orchestration—it is essential to recognize that the physical (i.e., L1) and data link (i.e., L2) layers of the protocol stack form the foundational substrate upon which all semantic-aware capabilities ultimately depend. These lower layers are not merely passive transport mechanisms; they are active participants in the dynamic optimization and adaptation required by semantic systems.

To realize the full potential of semantic communication within O-RAN, both L1 and L2 must be reimagined to support semantic-awareness in a manner that is deeply integrated, context-sensitive, and computationally efficient.

At L1, the traditional role has been to handle modulation, coding, signal processing, and physical resource mapping. In conventional systems, these operations are agnostic to the meaning of the data being transmitted. That is, they treat all bits as equal in importance, aiming to deliver them reliably and quickly through techniques like Hybrid Automatic Repeat reQuest (HARQ), beamforming, and Adaptive Modulation and Coding (AMC). However, semantic communication changes this premise. It introduces asymmetry in the value of information, wherein certain bits—those carrying core semantic meaning—are far more important than others. This creates a need for semantics-aware physical layer strategies that can, for instance, prioritize the encoding and retransmission of critical data segments, while tolerating loss or degradation in segments that contribute little to the overall meaning. Such approaches necessitate redefining reliability metrics at L1. Instead of relying solely on Bit Error Rate (BER) or Block Error Rate (BLER), the system should consider semantic metrics that captures how well the received information preserves the intended meaning. This shift will require innovations in modulation schemes that can adapt not just to channel conditions but also to semantic priorities. For example, a deep learning-based encoder could map high-importance semantic units into more robust codewords, while less critical ones are mapped using higher-throughput but less reliable configurations.

Moreover, L1 must become dynamically reconfigurable to accommodate the variability of semantic content. In a traditional setup, resource allocation is scheduled based on predefined QoS profiles. Semantic-aware systems, in contrast, require on-the-fly reconfiguration of transmission parameters—such as power levels, subcarrier allocations, and antenna precoding—based on real-time semantic insights provided by higher layers or edge AI models. O-RAN's disaggregated architecture, especially the Near-RT RIC, provides a logical control point to facilitate this dynamic orchestration of physical layer behaviour through closed-loop feedback and policy enforcement.

L2, comprising the MAC with its direct relation with RLC, and Packet Data Convergence Protocol (PDCP) sublayers, plays an equally vital role in enabling semantic communication. At the MAC layer, scheduling algorithms must be enhanced to become semantics-aware, prioritizing packets not based on static service types—e.g., Enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB), Ultra Reliable Low Latency Communications (URLLC), but on the contextual value of their content. This means incorporating semantic metadata or tags into packet headers, which can then inform the scheduler about the urgency or relevance of each transmission.

The RLC layer, responsible for segmentation, reassembly, and ARQ retransmissions, presents a particularly interesting challenge. Traditional RLC operations treat packet loss uniformly as a trigger for retransmission. However, in a semantic framework, it becomes important to ask whether retransmitting a particular segment is actually necessary from a meaning preservation standpoint. This leads to the concept of semantic-aware retransmission, where the system evaluates whether missing data materially impacts the user-perceived quality or application outcome before initiating costly recovery operations. Implementing such a mechanism requires the tight coupling of semantic inference modules with L2 operations, possibly through enriched metadata exchanges or real-time semantic scoring.

Similarly, PDCP must evolve to handle semantic compression, aggregation, and prioritization. Current header compression and ciphering techniques are content-agnostic, but semantic systems may benefit from PDCP functions that intelligently bundle related semantic units, discard redundant or non-essential elements, or apply content-aware encryption schemes that prioritize privacy for more sensitive semantic features.

Another important consideration is inter-layer coordination. Semantic awareness cannot be confined to any one layer; it must be implemented as a cross-layer feature. This implies that L1 and L2 must be able to receive policy directives or semantic annotations from higher layers (e.g., from the RIC or from edge semantic modules), and respond adaptively within their operational constraints. This is particularly relevant in O-RAN environments, where the split architecture allows for centralized control and distributed execution. Enhancing the interfaces between RIC applications (i.e., xApps and rApps) and the radio protocol stack becomes essential for enabling such cross-layer intelligence.

In terms of implementation, semantic enhancements at L1/L2 will likely involve the deployment of AI/ML models directly at the PHY-MAC interface. These models can be trained to recognize patterns in semantic metadata, channel conditions, and traffic profiles, and make predictive decisions about scheduling, retransmission, or modulation strategies. The use of programmable baseband units and hardware accelerators will be key to ensuring these enhancements can be realized within the real-time constraints of wireless networks.

Implementing semantics-aware enhancements at L1/L2 requires a tightly coupled orchestration framework that spans from high-level semantic reasoning down to the physical behaviour of radio links. Within the O-RAN architecture, this coordination is made possible through the synergistic operation of the RICs: the Near-RT RIC and the Non-RT RIC.

The Near-RT RIC, designed to manage functions within a timescale of 10 ms to 1 s, plays a pivotal role in realizing semantics-aware operations at L1/L2. It serves as the decision-making engine for near-instantaneous control tasks such as radio resource scheduling, interference mitigation, and handover optimization. By extending its capabilities with semantic awareness—delivered via AI-powered xApps—the Near-RT RIC can begin to evaluate not only the channel and user-level metrics but also the semantic relevance of each packet or flow. This enables the RIC to drive new forms of intelligent scheduling, semantic-based HARQ prioritization, and adaptive retransmission control that align with meaning-centric KPIs rather than purely physical-layer throughput.

To support these tasks, the Near-RT RIC must receive rich semantic metadata from external entities such as MEC applications or semantic modules embedded in UEs. The recently introduced Y1 interface, which connects the Near-RT RIC with external analytics consumers, becomes a cornerstone here. By evolving this interface into a bidirectional, semantics-capable data conduit, the Near-RT RIC can gather context insights and semantic KPIs while also disseminating policies that shape L1/L2 behaviour dynamically.

Complementing this real-time orchestration is the Non-RT RIC, which handles functions over longer timescales (seconds to hours) and focuses on training, optimizing, and governing AI/ML models, including those used for semantic inference and low-layer control. The Non-RT RIC serves as the policy brain of the RAN, enabling rApps to analyse historical data, optimize semantic model parameters, define system-wide policies, and update semantic prioritization rules. These policies are then fed into the Near-RT RIC through the A1 interface, shaping its real-time decisions while ensuring alignment with broader network objectives and constraints.

2.3 RAN Interference Management Based on Non-RT RIC in 5G Networks

To efficiently operate 5G RAN under a variety of environments and use cases that change over time, it is important to intelligently manage the RAN and reprogram its configuration dynamically as needed. The Non-RT RIC as defined by O-RAN ALLIANCE can serve a key role towards

such programmable RAN, by supporting AI-based rApps that can infer the best RAN operating configurations based on gathered information from RAN [PBD+23]. In this deliverable, a series of rApps developed based on the O-RAN Software Community (O-RAN SC)'s Non-RT RIC is presented. These rApps together provide localization, UE throughput prediction, and cross-cell interference management functionalities, which brings a practical perspective to improve overall network efficiency via leveraging the interactions with L1/L2 functionalities. The rApps have been successfully integrated with a commercial-grade 5G system deployed in the Singapore University of Technology and Design (SUTD) campus. The developed rApps could help better understand the effect of interference in goal-oriented communications.

2.3.1 Context and motivation

The Open-RAN architecture paradigm is revolutionizing the RAN landscape with its emphasis on open interfaces, disaggregation, virtualization, and software defined intelligent control. Central to the O-RAN transformation is the RIC, particularly the Non-RT RIC [ORAN2ARC], which houses rApps that enable sophisticated management and optimization of RAN operations. These rApps harness AI/ML algorithms for tasks like policy management and network optimization, addressing challenges such as energy savings, cell interference management, and network reliability. In this section, the O-RAN SC Non-RT RIC is integrated with a commercial-grade open RAN 5G network deployed in the SUTD campus. A suite of rApps—Localization, UE throughput prediction, Predictive maintenance, and interference management—were developed and deployed, which together achieved significant end-to-end performance gain by reducing the interference in a real-world dynamic environment.

Figure 2-5 System architecture of rApps with SUTD 5G network.

2.3.2 Proposed framework and setup

In the setup, the O-RAN SC's Non-RT RIC were used and integrated with the O-RAN-based private 5G networks deployed in SUTD campus, as shown in Figure 2-5. The SUTD 5G network consists of one indoor cell and one outdoor cell, operating at the same N78 band.¹ The outdoor cell consists of 2 radio units (RUs) that jointly cover a drone arena and the corridor areas of

¹ The N78 band is a 5G frequency range from 3300 MHz to 3800 MHz, also known as the 3.5 GHz band or C-band.

multiple floors (i.e., levels 4, 5, and 6). The indoor cells cover the lab at level 3 and two classrooms at level 5. The level 5 indoor cell overlaps with the outdoor cell at level 5's corridor area, resulting in an interference zone there (as highlighted in Figure 2-5). Since the network was commissioned in the summer of 2022, it has been observed that the inter-cell interference at the level 5 corridor can cause significant performance degradation in some use cases, including one that involves patrolling 5G robots along the corridor of level 5. In this deliverable, a suite of rApps were designed and developed to address the interference drawback and demonstrate the end-to-end flow of the control to resolve the issue.

A suite of rApps for interference management in a private 5G network

Figure 2-5 presents the architecture of the demo system. The functionalities and collaboration details of key components in the proposed architecture are as follows.

- The Virtual Event Streaming (VES) Collector acquires Key Performance Metrics (KPM) from individual UE in the RAN. Then, the KPM data is streamed into InfluxDB² for storage and subsequent processing by other rApps.
- Localization-rApp is to estimate UE location using radio metrics. The rApp outputs a floor indication rather than providing UE's precise GPS location. Consequently, this rApp is considered as a classifier that denotes the specific floor level of the UE.
- UE-TP-rApp is a UE-level throughput prediction rApp that predicts the traffic throughput of UE based on its recent measured radio signal metrics, such as Received Signal Strength Indicator (RSSI), Reference Signal Received Power (RSRP), Modulation Coding Scheme (MCS), Physical Resource Block (PRB) usage, and throughput.
- IM-rApp is an Interference Management (IM) rApp that consists of 2 stages: (1) it consults the outputs from the Localization-rApp and UE-TP-rApp to detect whether a UE is entering the interference zone, (2) it adjusts the neighbouring RU's transmission (TX) power to reduce the area of interference zone. Specifically, based on the output of the 1st stage, the IM-rApp will send the configuration management (CM) to appropriate RU of the neighbouring cell via the O1 interface (standardized by O-RAN ALLIANCE O1 Specification) to reduce TX power either: (i) by 3 dB (i.e., 50% reduction) if there are still active UEs covered by the neighbouring cell, or (ii) otherwise reduce by 5 dB (i.e., 70% reduction). The two numbers of reduction were chosen based on measurements of the area of the interference zone after adjusting TX power on actual deployment.
- PM-rApp is a predictive maintenance rApp that monitors the actual number of active RUs within a cell and their transmission power states based on UE measurement. It provides a useful tool for network management systems to monitor the actual configurations in the network. The interference management use case helps confirm that the RU transmission power adjustment takes effect.

Data collection and pre-processing

The study involved collecting a set of KPMs from a 5G Samsung S22 Ultra smartphone across various configurations at the SUTD building 2. The KPMs, including RSRP, RSRQ, SINR, and others, are essential for rApps to detect network issues in real-time. In the experiment, data (at a sampling rate of 2 Hz) were collected by moving around the corridors of each floor at walking speed for three rounds. The collected dataset spans a total duration of around 20 minutes and covers a real-world environment on the campus. The data collection was designed to mimic a typical network testing process conducted by a telco when commissioning a new network.

In the preprocessing phase, null values were removed and a cross-correlation analysis was performed among the KPM features, setting a threshold of 0.98 to ensure feature independence.

² <https://www.influxdata.com/>

The highest correlation score observed was 0.973 between SINR and RSRP. Subsequently, the dataset was normalized and split into a 70:30 training-to-test ratio.

2.3.3 Experimental results and demo

A range of ML models has been developed and tested, including both classical ML models: Support Vector Machines (SVM), Random Forest, linear classifier, linear regression, and XGBoost; and deep learning models: Deep Neural Networks (DNN), and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) for the rApps. These models were designed to handle either instance-based or sequence-based (i.e., a window of recent historical KPMs) inputs, with the latter generally providing superior performance with a slightly larger model size. The evaluation results are given in Table 2-1 Results summary of various AI-driven rApps.. A detailed discussion on the results is provided as below.

For the *Localization-rApp*, the best-performing LSTM model can classify a UE’s floor level with an accuracy of 91.1%. In predicting UE throughput (*UE-TP-rApp*), the sequence-based DNN model excels with an R2 score of 0.90.

For the *IM-rApp*, the LSTM model can achieve the highest accuracy of 90.1%. Finally, for *PM-rApp*, the DNN model achieves an accuracy of 99.1%.

Overall, the experimental results demonstrate the efficacy of sequence-based ML models, particularly DNN and LSTM, using real-world RAN data, to support the various use cases. The experiments show that these rApps can work together and reduce the interfering RUs’ transmission power when there is UE entering the interference zones, hence significantly reducing the negative impact caused by network interference.

Table 2-1 Results summary of various AI-driven rApps.

rApp	Input	Best Model	Metric	Inf(μ s)
Localization	Inst.	XGBoost	Acc: 84.4%	2.1
	Seq.	LSTM	Acc: 91.1%	27.4
UE-TP	Inst.	DNN	R ² : 0.84	0.7
	Seq.	DNN	R ² : 0.90	0.4
IM	Seq.	LSTM	Acc: 90.1	14.0
PM	Inst.	XGBoost	Acc: 92.6%	1.5
	Seq.	DNN	Acc: 99.1%	3.8

N.B.: “Acc” refers to classification accuracy, “R²” to regression determination. “Best Model” is the top performer in each task.

Demo

For a pre-recorded demonstration of the Localization, UETP, PM, and IM rApps in action within the OSC’s Non-RT RIC, refer to the video demo available online.³

2.3.4 Conclusions and future directions

In this demo, the O-RAN SC Non-RT RIC was integrated into commercial-grade private 5G networks, laying a robust foundation for intelligent network management. The deployment of ML models, particularly those handling sequential input, significantly outperformed their instance-based counterparts. The top-performing models attained over 90% accuracy across all applications while maintaining an inference time below 30 ms. It is expected that the experiences gained from this project could be useful for future efforts that integrate intelligence into

³ <http://tinyurl.com/SUTDrApps>

real world 5G systems. Further implementations based on these experiments will be presented in a collaborative way with other partners, especially regarding the interference management-based computation offloading in semantic image transmission [6GGOALS-D25].

3 L1/L2 Functionalities and Control Strategies for Semantic Communications

This section presents L1/L2 functionalities and control strategies tailored for semantic and goal-oriented communications. Section 3.1 addresses semantic content selection in IoT scenarios, introducing a MAC protocol for timely retrieval of fresh and relevant data, and proposing its optimization to maximize EE. Section 3.2 investigates heterogeneous IoT scenarios, where devices operating in the pull and push communication modes coexist in a network. An optimization of the MAC frame design is proposed to maximize the probability of successful communication coexistence by allocating the time slots dedicated to pull and push. Section 3.3 addresses the scenario of collaborative edge inference, proposing a method for device grouping based jointly on the semantic features of their data and the channel link conditions. The proposed grouping method allows achieving high task accuracy levels with reduced communication overhead. Finally, Section 3.4 discusses the integration of the presented functionalities and strategies into the 6G-GOALS Architecture.

3.1 Energy-Efficient IoT Sensing Data Retrieval Through Wake-Up Radio

3.1.1 Context and motivation

Industrial IoT applications require energy-efficient strategies for data collection, guaranteeing the availability of fresh and relevant information for effective actuation. In Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs), where a sink node pulls observations from sensor nodes through queries, *wake-up radio* has been considered a promising technology for realizing high EE. In a basic setup, sensors are equipped with two radios, a *primary radio interface* for data transmission and a wake-up radio for receiving wake-up requests. The central idea is to keep the sensor's primary radio interface switched off during idle periods, turning it on upon a data collection request sent by the sink and received through the wake-up radio [PMK+17]. Such a strategy significantly decreases the sensors' energy consumption and, consequently, improves the EE, since the wake-up receiver function is based on frugal hardware and a simple detection scheme, dissipating considerably less power than the primary radio. Nevertheless, the EE improvement achieved by wake-up radio is not only the result of creating low-power sleep states for the sensors but also of the possibility of activating, among a vast population of sensors, only those few that contain data relevant to the application. These characteristics make wake-up radio a suitable technology for developing low powered and energy-autonomous IoT devices [6GGOALS-D21].

The signalling used to wake up the sensors can embed low-rate information through modulation schemes like On-Off Keying (OOK). With that, and based on a predefined wake-up condition, the sink can select the set of nodes that will transmit their observations by changing the content of *wake-up signalling*. Accordingly, the wake-up signal can be used to wake up sensors based on unique node identifiers or group identifiers, in schemes called *identity-based wake-up* [YKA+16]. Furthermore, the wake-up signal can also be employed to activate sensors dynamically based on their current readings, in schemes named *Content-based Wake-up (CoWu)* [SYH+21]. Traditionally, in CoWu, the wake-up signal encodes a threshold such that only the nodes that observe values greater than the threshold are activated. By carefully controlling such a threshold, it is possible to collect data efficiently under different objectives, such as collecting the k highest sensor readings and retrieving readings that fall within a certain range.

This section aims to investigate the EE improvement of CoWu data collection in a WSN for the timely retrieval of the top- k readings from the sensors by a predefined deadline. Initially, to characterize the energy performance, an analytical energy consumption model for the sensors is derived, accounting for the CoWu wake-up condition and the data transmission. Then, the average *Top-k Query Age-of-Information* (k -QAoI) is derived and leveraged to minimize the energy consumption of the data collection process while meeting a constraint on information freshness. Numerical results compare the CoWu data collection method with baselines, corroborating its significant EE gains and validating the proposed optimization strategy.

3.1.2 System model and problem statement

The proposed data collection method is illustrated in Figure 3-1, where a sink node queries the sensor nodes employing CoWu. In this scenario, the sensors monitor a real-valued random process with domain constrained by $[V_{min}, V_{max}]$. The goal of the sink is to collect the k highest sensor readings, namely the top- k readings, before a given deadline. To ensure that only the sensors with relevant data will wake up and transmit their observations, the sink embeds a threshold V_{th} in the wake-up signal, which depends on the characteristics of the monitored process. Then, after receiving the wake-up signal and decoding V_{th} , a sensor compares its current reading with this threshold value, waking up if the reading is above the threshold.

Figure 3-1 System model for top- k data collection from IoT devices.

To ensure the reception of fresh information by the deadline, the sink controls the timing parameter ζ . Specifically, this parameter determines how long the wake-up signal will be transmitted earlier than the deadline. In practice, this parameter will affect two important aspects of timely data collection. First, given that the sensors sample the monitored process after detecting the wake-up signal, the timing parameter will impact the freshness of the readings by the deadline. Second, the parameter will determine the time window size available for data transmission by the sensors. Hence, on the one hand, a small timing parameter and, consequently, a short time window, result in fresh readings but increase the risk that the sink does not receive all relevant readings by the deadline due to successive communication errors. On the other hand, while increasing the likelihood of receiving all the relevant data, a large timing parameter increases the risk of having outdated readings by the deadline.

For sending their observations to the sink, the sensors adopt the p -persistent Carrier Sense Multiple Access (CSMA) protocol through the primary radio interface. Accordingly, the sensors that wake up will conduct carrier sensing, transmitting their observations with the probability p when the channel is detected to be idle. Retransmissions might occur in the case of collision or erasure. With the transmission probability p and other communication parameters, it is possible

to compute the data collection delay, which will be used further to improve the EE of the data collection method.

To model the sensors' energy consumption, only the energy consumed by the primary radio interface can be accounted for, as the energy consumed by the wake-up receiver is negligible compared to it. Accordingly, the sensors' energy consumption depends chiefly on the time they spend conducting carrier sensing and transmitting their observations. Hence, the total energy consumption results in

$$E_{\text{total}}(N) = \sum_{n=1}^N \xi_T t_{\text{tx}}^n + \xi_R t_{\text{rx}}^n,$$

where N is the number of sensors, and ξ_T (ξ_R) and t_{tx}^n (t_{rx}^n) are the power consumption and total time spent in the transmitting (receiving) state, respectively. By analysing the data collection method and the data transmission with p-persistent CSMA, the total energy consumption of CoWu is

$$E_{\text{total}}^{\text{Co}}(N) = \sum_{w=0}^N P_d(w) E_{\text{total}}(w|N).$$

where $P_d(w)$ is the probability that w out of N sensors wake up. For the detailed derivations, see [SKL+25].

To measure information freshness of the data collection method, the k -QAol is considered. Specifically, the k -QAol encompasses the *cost of update delay*, which quantifies the penalty associated with stale information at the receiver, and also the relevance of the retrieved information based on the top- k readings [6GGOALS-D24]. For the CoWu data collection, the average k -QAol is derived as

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\Delta}_k^{\text{Co}}(\zeta) &= \sum_{w=0}^N P_d(w) \sum_{w_s=0}^w P_s(w_s|w, \zeta) \sum_{r=0}^{\min(w_s, k)} P_k(r|w, w_s) \\ &\times \frac{r \min(f_s(\zeta), A_{\max}) + (k-r) \min(f_s(\Gamma), A_{\max})}{k}. \end{aligned}$$

where $P_s(w_s|w, \zeta)$ is the probability that w_s out of w wake-up nodes succeed in data transmission by the deadline for a given ζ , while $P_k(r|w, w_s)$ is the probability that r sensors that contain readings among the top- k succeed in data transmission by the deadline. In addition, $f_s(\zeta)$ denotes an age function that reflect the dynamics of the monitored physical process, Γ denotes the time elapsed since the latest received packet was generated at the deadline when data transmission fails, and A_{\max} denotes the maximum value of the cost of update delay.

This work aims to investigate how much energy consumption can be reduced by applying a CoWu method for data collection. Therefore, the objective of optimization is to determine the wake-up control and transmission parameters that minimize energy consumption, while guaranteeing a certain level of k -QAol. Formally, the optimization problem can be defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{V_{\text{th}}, p, \zeta} & E_{\text{total}}^{\text{Co}}(N) \\ \text{s.t.} & \bar{\Delta}_k^{\text{Co}}(\zeta) \leq \gamma_{\text{th}}, \\ & V_{\text{th}} \in [V_{\min}, V_{\max}] \\ & p \in (0, 1] \\ & \zeta \in \mathbb{Z}^+ \end{aligned}$$

The optimization variables are the wake-up threshold, the transmission probability, and the timing parameter. Meanwhile, the objective function is the total energy consumption. The first constraint ensures data freshness by guaranteeing that the k -QAol is below a threshold γ_{th} . Then, the remaining constraints ensure the optimization variables lie within their feasible domains. As

the optimization problem is non-convex and analytically challenging, an approximate but efficient solution is proposed by decoupling the optimization variables.

3.1.3 Proposed methodology and solution

To minimize energy consumption in the proposed data collection method while guaranteeing a certain level of k -QAol, the following solution is proposed. Initially, the optimal transmission probability is obtained analytically. Then, the optimal wake-up threshold and the timing parameter are obtained through a grid search.

First, to realize information freshness at the deadline, the transmission probability is optimized to minimize the data collection delay. The optimal value can be obtained analytically and is given by

$$p_{\text{opt}}^*(m) = \begin{cases} 1, & m = 1, \\ \approx \frac{\sqrt{m^2 + 2m(m-1)(L-1)} - m}{m(m-1)(L-1)}, & m > 1. \end{cases}$$

where m is the number of active sensor nodes and L is the data packet length in time slots. The steps to obtain the analytical solution are detailed in [SKL+25].

Second, with the optimal transmission probability, the wake-up threshold and timing parameter are optimized according to the following optimization problem

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{C}(N) &= \min_{\{\zeta, V_{\text{th}}\}} E_{\text{total}}^{\text{Co}}(N) \\ \text{s.t. } \bar{\Delta}_k^{\text{Co}}(\zeta) &\leq \gamma_{\text{th}}, \end{aligned}$$

which minimizes the energy consumption while maintaining the average k -QAol below a certain threshold. Since the optimization problem is non-convex, a grid search is employed to compute a solution. Specifically, the search is done by sampling the optimization variables and evaluating the objective function for each combination of parameter values.

3.1.4 Results

The performance of the data collection method and the proposed optimization were evaluated through numerical simulations. To demonstrate the gains in EE of the CoWu data collection method, its performance is compared with 3 baselines: 1) Round-robin scheduling, where all sensors wake up and transmit their observations in dedicated time slots; 2) q -based random wake-up, where the sensors wake up with probability q regardless of their readings; and 3) Genie-aided scheme, where the sink perfectly knows the nodes that contain the top- k observations and collects them through the identity-based wake-up method.

Figure 3-2 depicts the achievable k -QAol and total energy consumption region, which were obtained by increasing the wake-up threshold while maintaining the other parameters constant. The total energy consumption increases with the threshold, resulting from the higher number of sensors waking up. It can be seen that the k -QAol can be improved by increasing the energy consumption, while an energy budget that is too small will degrade the k -QAol, as the data collection process is more likely to fail. The CoWu data collection method consistently achieves a smaller energy consumption than the baselines, justifying its usage to improve the EE.

Further, Figure 3-3 shows the k -QAol against the timing parameter. It can be noticed that, when the other parameters are maintained constant, there is a timing parameter value that minimizes the k -QAol. On the one hand, when the timing parameter is lower than the optimal, the k -QAol degrades due to the short communication window, resulting in failing transmissions due to channel congestion. On the other hand, when it is higher than the optimal value, the observations are acquired much earlier than the deadline, becoming obsolete and decreasing the k -QAol.

Figure 3-2 Achievable k -QAoI against the total energy consumption.

Figure 3-3 k -QAoI against the timing parameter.

Figure 3-4 Optimal timing parameter against the parameter of the exponential age function.

Then, Figure 3-4 and Figure 3-5 show the behaviour of the proposed data collection method when changing characteristics of the monitored process. Specifically, the speed the physical process changes over time increases with α . In Figure 3-4, it can be perceived that the optimal timing parameter decreases with α . This happens because, to collect fresh observations, it is

necessary to query the sensors closer to the deadline. In Figure 3-5, the optimal k -QAoI increases with α because the collected observations become obsolete faster when the monitored process changes at a higher speed. Noticeably, there is a significant performance gap between the CoWu and the round-robin scheduling for higher α values.

Lastly, Figure 3-6 depicts the minimum energy consumption against the number of sensors. It can be seen that the CoWu data collection method achieves smaller energy consumption than round-robin scheduling, thanks to its capacity to wake up only the sensors that contain relevant readings. Hence, it has been demonstrated that data collection through CoWu is promising for increasing the EE, especially for large sensor populations.

Figure 3-5 Optimal k -QAoI against the parameter of the exponential age function.

Figure 3-6 Minimum energy consumption against the number of sensor nodes.

3.1.5 Conclusions and future directions

This section investigated the problem of energy-efficient and timely retrieval of top- k observations in WSNs under information freshness constraints. To analyse the energy performance and information freshness achieved with CoWu data collection, analytical expressions for the energy consumption and average k -QAoI were derived accounting for the wake-up condition and data transmission process. Then, an optimization method was proposed to minimize the energy consumption of data collection while guaranteeing a certain level of k -QAoI. Specifically, the proposed method was designed to optimize 3 key parameters of CoWu: the timing parameter of the wake-up signalling, the wake-up threshold, and the sensors' transmission probability. Numerical evaluations showed that the optimized CoWu data collection achieves remarkable EE gains compared to traditional methods, especially for large sensor populations. Future investigations

might include the optimization of the wake-up control to define the optimal sensor sampling time in the data collection process.

3.2 Efficient Coexistence of Pull and Push Communication for IoT Data Retrieval

3.2.1 Context and motivation

In IoT data retrieval, a sink node can benefit from two basic communication modes to collect data from wireless sensor nodes. The first mode is *pull-based*, where the sink retrieves data from specific sensors through queries. Meanwhile, the second one is *push-based*, where the sensors decide when to send data to the sink. The choice between these modes depends on the application goals, as they work with different mechanisms and types of IoT devices, yielding different trade-offs. For instance, push-based communication enables controlling who sends data based on the relevance of their information, while pull-based communication prioritizes the autonomy of the sensors. In heterogeneous IoT scenarios [6GGOALS-D21], both communication modes can coexist, giving rise to the new problem of efficiently integrating them in the wireless access. This coexistence scenario was investigated by few works in the literature, such as [PSX+21] and [TMC+24].

For this reason, this section addresses the problem of the coexistence of push and pull communication in wireless access, where both communication modes share the same radio resources for data transmission [6GGOALS-D23]. Ultimately, the objective is to design the optimal frame structure to maximize the average success probability for the communication coexistence, determining the amount of resources reserved for pull and push communication. To that end, analytical expressions for the query satisfaction rate and probability of successful access are derived to evaluate the performance of the pull and push modes, respectively. Then, these two metrics are combined into a joint metric that can be employed to optimize the performance in the coexistence scenario. Numerical results are presented to validate the derived analytical results and demonstrate the trade-offs that can be achieved by the pull and push communication modes. It is worth mentioning that the investigation in this deliverable focuses on the optimal frame design for the coexistence scenario, while the analysis in [6GGOALS-D42] introduces a complementary study of this framework applied for communication under timing constraints.

3.2.2 System model and proposed framework

The coexistence scenario considers a sink node, which can be a base station or access point, that collects data from two types of sensor nodes: some that work with pull-based communication, while others work with push-based communication. The MAC frame model shown in Figure 3-7 is considered for uplink data transmission. The system operates in a time-slotted framework, where the frame of duration T_{frame} comprises F time slots of duration τ , and is split into two segments of duration T_{pull} and T_{push} dedicated to pull- and push-based communication, respectively.

Figure 3-7 Proposed MAC frame structure for pull and push communication coexistence.

The pull-based sensors use wake-up radio to transmit data upon queries emitted by the sink. Assuming the *identity-based wake-up* scheme, each query contains an identifier of the device to pull data, avoiding transmission collisions by activating only one sensor per pull slot. Furthermore, the new queries are created following a Poisson Point Process (PPP) with an average arrival rate of λ_q queries/s. With that, each pull slot is divided into two main phases: 1) Transmission by the sink of the wake-up signal with the sensor identifier; and 2) Data payload transmission by the queried sensor. Therefore, the time dedicated to pull-based communication is

$$T_{\text{pull}} = Q(k_w + k_t)\tau,$$

where Q is the number of scheduled pull slots, while $k_w\tau$ and $k_t\tau$ are the durations of the wake-up signal and data payload time slots, respectively. It is worth mentioning that, since only one sensor is queried per pull slot, Q is also the number of queries that can be served within a frame.

The push-based sensors operate intermittently, using a Framed ALOHA scheme for transmitting data to the sink. The packet generation follows a PPP with average arrival rate of λ_p packets/s. Each push slot is divided into two phases: 1) Data payload transmission by the sensor; and 2) Acknowledgement transmission by the sink. When two or more sensors decide to transmit in the same push slot, a collision occurs, and all the transmitted packets in that slot are lost. Hence, the time reserved for push communication is

$$T_{\text{push}} = T_{\text{frame}} - T_{\text{pull}} = (F - Q(k_w + k_t))\tau$$

It can be noted that the durations of the frame segments dedicated to both pull- and push-based communication are functions of the number of pull slots Q . Given that, this work aims to characterize how Q affects the performance of each communication mode, and then propose a MAC frame design to optimize the joint performance of the pull and push sensors.

3.2.3 Performance evaluation and optimization

Before proposing the optimal MAC frame design, it is necessary to characterize the performance of each communication mode. For pull-based communication, the performance is given by the probability of serving the queries. By employing results from queueing theory, such a probability can be approximated by

$$p_s^{(q)} \approx 1 - B(Q, \bar{n}_q) = 1 - \frac{\frac{\bar{n}_q^Q}{Q!}}{\sum_{i=0}^Q \frac{\bar{n}_q^i}{i!}}.$$

where $B(Q, \bar{n}_q)$ is the Erlang-B formula and \bar{n}_q is the average number of queries in a frame.

On the other hand, for push-based communication, the performance is given by throughput, which is related to the probability of successful push access. Therefore, under the Framed ALOHA scheme and collision channel assumptions, this probability is given by:

$$p_s^{(p)} = \begin{cases} (1 + \bar{n}_p) e^{-\bar{n}_p}, & \text{if } k_a = 1, \\ e^{-\bar{n}_p} \frac{k_a e^{\frac{(k_a-1)\bar{n}_p}{k_a}} - 1}{k_a - 1}, & \text{if } k_a > 1. \end{cases}$$

where \bar{n}_p is the average number of push packets in a frame and k_a is the number of push slots. It is worth noting that, from Figure 3-7, k_a can be rewritten as a function of Q :

$$k_a = F - k_c - Q(k_w + k_t)$$

where k_c is the number of time slots dedicated to control signalling in the frame segment reserved for push-based communication. All the derivations are detailed in [CSS+24].

With the individual performance metrics for pull and push communication, it is possible to define a performance trade-off metric suitable for the coexistence scenario. Accordingly, the weighted average success probability for the communication coexistence is:

$$p_s = w_q p_s^{(q)} + w_p p_s^{(p)},$$

where w_q and w_p are positive weights that reflect the target requirements of pull- and push-based communications. Since both the probabilities of serving the queries and of successful push access depend on Q , it is possible to find the value of Q that maximizes this joint metric. Given the straightforward dependence of $p_s^{(q)}$ and $p_s^{(p)}$ on Q , a simple searching algorithm can be employed to find the Q that maximizes p_s .

3.2.4 Results

Numerical results were implemented to analyse the proposed MAC frame optimization for the coexistence of pull and push communication. To run the simulations, the weight values in the success probability for the communication coexistence were set to $w_q = \frac{\lambda_q}{\lambda_q + \lambda_p}$ and $w_p = \frac{\lambda_p}{\lambda_q + \lambda_p}$.

Figure 3-8 depicts the average success probability for the communication coexistence against the number of pull slots, considering different values of the query arrival rate and push packet arrival rate. It can be seen that specific values of Q maximize the coexistence performance for each setup, confirming the necessity of optimizing the MAC frame design. Furthermore, as expected, the maximum of p_s is achieved with a Q value that increases consistently with λ_q , since more slots dedicated to pull-based communication are needed to serve the queries arriving at higher rates.

Figure 3-8 Success probability for the communication coexistence against the number of pull slots.

Figure 3-9 Success probability for the communication coexistence against the push packet arrival rate.

Lastly, Figure 3-9 depicts the average success probability for the communication coexistence against the push packet arrival rate, providing insights on the optimization of Q based on the system's input load. One can notice that, for a constant λ_q , the curves for different values of Q intersect at a specific arrival rate λ'_p . If $\lambda_p < \lambda'_p$, it is advisable to allocate more slots for pull communication, while the opposite is advisable when $\lambda_p > \lambda'_p$. Despite this result was shown for $Q \in \{1,10\}$, a similar rule can be derived for every pair of values for Q .

3.2.5 Conclusions and future directions

This section investigated the efficient coexistence of pull and push communication for IoT data retrieval. Initially, the performance of each communication mode was analysed, resulting in analytical expressions for the probability of serving the queries and the probability of successful push access. In the sequence, these expressions were combined to define the average success probability for the communication coexistence, a suitable metric for joint optimization of pull- and push-based communication by determining the amount of resources dedicated for each communication mode. Numerical results corroborated the effectiveness of the proposed optimization for the MAC frame design, showing the achievable trade-offs under different combinations of pull and push traffic loads. Future works will investigate the optimal performance in a longer time horizon, and incorporate the knowledge on the correlations among the traffic arrivals and data in the optimization.

3.3 Joint Channel and Semantic-aware Grouping for Effective Collaborative Edge Inference

3.3.1 Context and motivation

Edge AI is increasingly relevant as modern applications require real-time inference from distributed, resource-constrained devices such as IoT sensors and embedded systems. Unlike centralized cloud-based systems, edge devices offer advantages in latency, privacy, and bandwidth efficiency. However, their limited computational power and exposure to noisy or partial data pose challenges for achieving high inference accuracy.

In collaborative edge inference, devices cooperate by exchanging features or intermediate representations to improve inference, particularly when their own local data is corrupted or incomplete. Traditional approaches, as [LTG+20] and [KPH23], focus on the collaboration based on the semantic relevance (how useful the data is to the task) or the channel quality (how reliably data can be transmitted over wireless links). This may hinder performance when irrelevant data are shared over reliable channels, or relevant data are shared over unreliable channels.

The main motivation of this contribution is to jointly incorporate semantic and wireless link value to improve collaboration decisions, especially in environments with harsh wireless conditions. Therefore, a cross-layer approach that combines semantic awareness with wireless link quality to optimally group devices for collaboration is proposed, thereby maximizing inference accuracy, while keeping communication overhead as low as possible. Further details can be found in [MMS25]. The goal here is to filter information, reducing the information overhead when a device already has sufficient information and also avoid the transmission of information unrelated to the goal of a device.

3.3.2 System model and problem statement

As shown in Figure 3-10, the system consists of L edge devices, each capable of running a shared, pre-trained ML model F , which is split on two modules:

$$F(x_i) = F_{Dec} \circ F_{Enc}(x_i),$$

where x_i is the local input at device i (e.g., an image), F_{Enc} represents the feature extractor part of the model and F_{Dec} represents the decision-making head of the model.

Figure 3-10 System model for the edge inference problem with intermediate collaboration

Devices are divided into groups based on their input data, those that observe the same underlying event (or object) belong to the same latent group g . However, due to random corruption (e.g., occlusions), a device i observes a distorted version $x_i = M_i(x_g)$ of the ground truth with probability p_p . Otherwise, they receive the full observation. It is important to highlight that, prior to the key-query matching, no device is aware of being part of a group or which devices are in the same latent group, as it only perceives its local observation.

Each device can share its encoded features, also called intermediate information, $o_i = \mathcal{F}_{Enc}(x_i)$ with the other devices through a wireless link modelled as a additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN) channel. If a device j sends its features, the information received by device i is:

$$y_{ij}^c = \mathcal{C}\{o_j\},$$

where \mathcal{C} represents the communication system.

The final input to the decision head at device i is formed by combining its own features with those received from collaborators, y_c^i , using a feature combiner F_{Comb} :

$$y_i^g = F_{Comb}(F_{Enc}(x_i), y_c^i)$$

Which is then used to perform the inference task by using the decision model as:

$$\hat{y}_i = F_{Dec}(y_i^g)$$

The goal is to collaborative infer \hat{y}_i with high accuracy. For this reason, the devices are allowed to use the communication system, not only to share their feature information, but also to identify potential devices with the information relevant as per the scope of improving their inference task performance.

3.3.3 Proposed methodology and solution

Given the above task, the proposed solution involves semantic grouping based on an attention mechanism similar to [LTG+20], but considering the link conditions. Each device generates a query μ and a key κ from its local intermediate information (local encoding) as:

$$\mu_i = \mathcal{Q}(o_i; \theta_q)$$

$$\kappa_i = \mathcal{K}(o_i, \theta_k)$$

where \mathcal{Q} and \mathcal{K} are small neural networks with parameters θ_q and θ_k , respectively. The key κ has size K .

Every device i multicasts its query μ_i , while each device locally retains its key κ_i . The query received by device j from device i is $\hat{\mu}_i^j = \mathcal{C}\{\mu_i\}$. Every device receives the query of all other devices and computes a matching score through scaled general attention, which quantifies both semantic relevance and channel reliability. The matching score for a device j receiving query from device i is m_{ij} :

$$m_{ij} = \frac{\kappa_j^\top W_i^j \hat{\mu}_i^j}{\sqrt{K}}$$

Differently from previous works where W is a learnable parameter without any dependencies, here $W_{ij} = \mathcal{W}(\gamma_{ji}^d, \gamma_{ij}^q)$ is modelled as a channel-aware weight matrix that adapts the attention score based on the estimated signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) of the data transmission from j to i , γ_{ji}^d , and the SNR of the query transmission from i to j , γ_{ij}^q .

All scores are then normalized using a softmax across each row:

$$\bar{m}_{ij} = \frac{\exp(m_{ij})}{\sum_k \exp(m_{ik})}$$

This results in a communication graph where edges represent the relevance of device j 's data to device i , modulated by channel quality. This is represented as a matrix with its elements being the normalized matching scores. To further reduce overhead, a pruning threshold ρ can be applied, by zeroing the elements of the matrix below a certain threshold as:

$$\bar{m}_{ij}^\rho = \bar{m}_{ij} \cdot \mathbb{1}\{\bar{m}_{ij} \geq \rho\}$$

This is done to ignore connections below a threshold, so that only data with normalized matching score above a threshold are transmitted. This limits the communication overhead, but computation of the matching score still happens, as it is needed to build the matching matrix.

Lastly, the final aggregation takes into consideration the matching scores as weights:

$$y_i^g = \sum_{j=1}^L \bar{m}_{ij}^\rho \cdot y_{ij}^c$$

Only the key and query networks \mathcal{C} and \mathcal{K} , and the attention matrix \mathcal{W} , are trained. The encoder and decoder remain fixed, making the system lightweight and compatible with pre-trained models.

Communication system considerations

The flow of information in this system follows as:

- Each device transmits its query through a sidelink multicast transmission to all other related devices, which is controlled by the network to exclude any device in the area not related to the task.
- The matching score m_{ij} is transmitted via uplink control channel to the network, as it is a system information needed to control the semantic grouping.
- The network creates the groups and sends the control information with the details for the sidelink data transmission via unicast for each transmitter and with the normalized-matching score for each receiver.

3.3.4 Results

Experiments use the Imagenette⁴ image classification dataset, with MobileNetV3-Small [HSC+2019] as the backbone. The size of the intermediate information is of 4000 floating points. 16 devices are considered to be divided into 4 groups. Data corruption is simulated by masking 40% of each image with probability 0.8. Two SNR scenarios are evaluated:

- Uniform scenario: SNRs are sampled from the uniform distribution in the interval of $[-10, 10]$ dB.
- Extreme scenario: The SNRs are samples from a discrete uniform distribution with values $\{-10, 10\}$ dB.

The semantic grouping solution, with and without link information (Proposed and Semantic-aware in the legend) is benchmarked against:

- Local inference (no collaboration)
- Full observation (oracle upper bound)
- Top-3 Channel (channel-only selection)

In the first set of results, the channel effect on query and data transmission is evaluated. For this, the effect of considering the link information in the method is analysed, comparing the semantic grouping solution trained for different query sizes with the other baselines in terms of accuracy.

Figure 3-11 Comparison of the different methods and scenarios in terms of accuracy for different query sizes. (a) intermediate data transmission is affected by channel errors, (b) intermediate data and query transmissions are affected by channel errors.

From Figure 3-11(a), one notice how adding the wireless link information improves performance, for both scenarios. In this case, the query can be of small size compared with the data, with the performance plateauing with a query size of 64 for the hardest case. However, Figure 3-11(b) shows that the effect of the channel on the query transmission makes the task much harder, as it needs a larger query to surpass the performance of the local-only solution. It also shows the importance of considering link information, as the link-unaware solution is unable to outperform local inference in the extreme scenario.

Next, the effect of pruning communication in the system is evaluated. It is assumed that only the data transmission is affected by channel and that the query size is 1024. These results, illustrated in Figure 3-12, show that communication pruning substantially reduces the number of transmissions without sacrificing accuracy, unless over-applied.

⁴ <https://github.com/fastai/imagenette>

Figure 3-12 Studying the effect of the communication pruning threshold. (a) Effect on the average number of sidelink connections per device. (b) Effect on accuracy.

3.3.5 Conclusions and future directions

In this work, a joint semantic and link-aware grouping framework for collaborative inference in wireless edge AI networks was proposed. Unlike prior approaches that consider only semantic similarity or channel strength, this method balances both dimensions via a learnable attention mechanism that adapts to real-time wireless conditions.

The main takeaways are:

- Cross-layer collaboration strategies are essential for robust and efficient edge AI.
- Reliable query exchange is more critical than data exchange due to the lightweight nature of queries and their role in determining group formation.
- Pruning based on matching scores effectively reduces communication load without degrading performance.

In terms of perspectives, evaluations are planned on other problems such as information retrieval (data sourcing) and Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) scenarios. Another interesting extension is the addition of query-aware data transmission, such that the data sent to a device is filtered for its needs.

3.4 Integration into the 6G-GOALS Architecture

This section outlines how the modules of the 6G-GOALS Architecture—introduced in Section 2.2—operate synergistically to enable the integration of the functionalities and strategies introduced in Section 3. Notably, [6GGOALS-D25] provides an in-depth analysis of integration aspects for a broader range of workflows, extending beyond network control. This includes a cross-layer perspective that spans from low-level physical layer processes to higher-layer interactions. The described workflows include semantic interpretation, decision-making based on semantic insights, semantic alignment, and training and deployment of semantic models.

The L1/L2 functionalities and control strategies discussed herein can be effectively integrated into the 6G-GOALS Architecture as applications deployed on the Non-RT or Near-RT S-RICs, depending on the required time scale of the network control actions. This is facilitated by the S-RICs' AI-native design, which supports dynamic network adaption based on semantic KPIs, and by their open interfaces that ensure interoperability with other O-RAN components for policy enforcement and feedback collection. The S-RICs are key bridges in the semantic control plane, enabling interactions of the rApps and xApps between CUs, DUs, edge and cloud applications, and UEs.

To gather network feedback, including both standard and semantic KPIs, communication between the Near-RT RIC and the CU via the E2 interface is essential. Additionally, extending the Y1 interface to support bidirectional communication enables the collection of feedback from

external entities such as edge and cloud applications. These mechanisms are particularly valuable in the MAC frame optimization described in Section 3.2, as they allow the system to capture traffic information from both push and pull devices, respectively. In contrast, the device grouping strategy presented in Section 3.3 relies on obtaining matching scores from UEs, which necessitates connectivity between the Near-RT S-RIC and the devices. In the absence of a direct interface, this information may be relayed through the RAN.

For policy enforcement, the F1 interface between the CU and DU enables dynamic resource allocation within the MAC frame. This facilitates the dynamic adaption of the MAC frame presented in Sections 3.1 and 3.2. However, in addition to frame adaption, the method for IoT data collection described in Section 3.1 also requires the adaption of transmission parameters at the devices—specifically, the wake-up threshold and the transmission probability. Similarly to the collection of UEs' feedback, this information may be relayed through the RAN due to the lack of a direct interface.

Overall, the 6G-GOALS Architecture provides a flexible and robust foundation for implementing RIC-centric, semantic-aware network control strategies across multiple components.

4 Conclusions

This deliverable has introduced the basic framework for implementing policy-based semantic control in the O-RAN architecture, introducing control strategies and L1/L2 functionalities developed based on semantic awareness. Starting from a review of the current O-RAN architecture, the required enhancements to support RIC-centric semantic control were identified. Specifically, the Non-RT and Near-RT RICs should be equipped with an improved Y1 interface to exchange semantic KPIs, configurations, and policy feedback with other O-RAN components and external applications. In addition, they need novel orchestration functionalities to coordinate the lifecycle of semantic models, including training, validation, deployment, and retirement operations. A further enhancement to enable O-RAN semantic control is the introduction of a Semantic Module and a Semantic Extractor at the device and application layer to interpret, filter, and extract semantic information and KPIs from raw data streams. Ultimately, the practical potential of the RIC-centric control was demonstrated with the deployment of ML-based rApps for localization, throughput prediction, predictive maintenance, and cross-cell interference management. The deployment serves as a basis to advance towards semantic use cases, supported by the semantic control plane established by the S-RICs.

L1/L2 functionalities and control strategies were proposed for three different use cases: 1) Semantic content selection in the IoT; 2) Heterogeneous IoT scenarios; and 3) Collaborative edge inference. For semantic content selection, a MAC protocol based on wake-up radio was proposed and optimized for timely retrieval of fresh and relevant data with high EE, achieved by reducing the IoT devices' power consumption. Then, targeting heterogeneous IoT scenarios, an optimization of the MAC frame design was developed to maximize the probability of successful communication coexistence in a scenario where devices use the pull and push modes. Finally, a device grouping strategy was introduced and evaluated, achieving high task accuracy levels with reduced communication overhead by jointly considering the semantic features of data and the channel link conditions.

Future advancements of Task 5.1 will investigate further control strategies and L1/L2 functionalities to facilitate semantic-aware control for the 6G-GOALS Use Cases. The aspects to be addressed include:

- *Control overheads:* Investigating the required signalling, metadata, and coordination necessary to manage and optimize the RAN is paramount to understanding the implications of semantic control on network latency, scalability, and efficiency.

- *Timing-reliability performance of the network control plane:* The timing-reliability performance of the semantic control plane is a potential bottleneck for network policy enforcement at different time scales, being a requirement that needs proper characterization in the context of semantic and goal-oriented communications.
- *Energy consumption of the network control plane:* The energy consumption of the semantic control plane must be characterized and optimized to enable energy-efficient semantic and goal-oriented communications.

In conclusion, the next actions aim to advance on the investigation of RIC-centric policy-based network control techniques with focus on characterizing the overhead and performance of the semantic control plane, and investigating the energy consumption of control functionalities to attain extreme energy efficiency.

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